

Synthesis and Characterisation some Mixed-Ligand Cyanonitrosyl $\{CrNO\}^5$ Complexes of Chromium(I) with some Aniline and 2-Pyrazolin-5-one Derivatives

R. C. MAURYA*, D. D. MISHRA, S. JAISWAL and I. B. KHAN

Coordination Chemistry Laboratory, Department of P. G. Studies and Research in Chemistry,
R. D. University, Jabalpur-482 001

Manuscript received 4 May 1990, revised 12 August 1992, accepted 18 August 1992

Mixed-ligand hexacoordinated cyanonitrosyl $\{CrNO\}^5$ complexes of chromium(I) of the compositions, $Cr(NO)(CN)_2(L)_2(H_2O)$ (where $L = N$ -methylaniline, N -ethyl-*o*-toluidine, N -ethyl-*p*-toluidine, N,N -dimethyl-*m*-toluidine or N -benzyl- N -ethylaniline) and $[Cr(NO)(CN)_2(L-L)(H_2O)]$ (where $L-L = 4$ -benzoyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-, 4-propionyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-, 4-chloroacetyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-, 4-*p*-chlorobenzoyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-, or 4-phenacyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) have been prepared in the solid state by the interaction of potassium pentacyanonitrosylchromate(I) monohydrate with the said ligands L and $L-L$. The complexes contain chromium(I) in a low-spin $\{CrNO\}^5$ electron configuration.

A perusal of the literature of neutral mixed-ligand nitrosyl complexes of chromium(I) having $\{CrNO\}^5$ electron configuration¹ reveals few reports on such complexes²⁻⁵. Although there has been considerable interest in the study of cyanonitrosyl $\{CrNO\}^5$ complexes of monovalent chromium⁶⁻⁸, there is no report on mixed-ligand cyanonitrosyl $\{CrNO\}^5$ complexes of chromium(I) with some N -alkyl, N,N -dialkyl and N -benzyl- N -alkylaniline(s), and with 2-pyrazolin-5-ones derived from 3-methyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one and certain acylchlorides, viz benzoyl chloride, propionyl chloride, chloroacetyl chloride, *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride and phenacyl chloride. We report here the synthesis of some neutral mixed-ligand cyanonitrosyl $\{CrNO\}^5$ complexes of chromium(I) with some N -alkylanilines, viz. N -methylaniline (NMA), N -ethyl-*o*-toluidine (NEOT), N -ethyl-*p*-toluidine (NEPT), N,N -dialkylaniline, viz. N,N -diethyl-*m*-toluidine (NNDEMT) and N -benzyl- N -alkylaniline, viz. N -benzyl- N -ethylaniline (NBNEA), and 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives, viz. 4-benzoyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-5-one (BTMP), 4-propionyl-1-(4'-tolyl)- (PTMP), 4-chloroacetyl-1-(4'-tolyl)- (CATMP), 4-*p*-chlorobenzoyl-1-(4'-tolyl)- (CBTMP) and 4-phenacyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (PHIMP). The interesting ligational behaviour of the both types of derivatives⁶ and biological importance⁷ of 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives, prompted us to undertake the present study.

Results and Discussion

The partial replacement of the cyano groups in the parent compound $K_3[Cr(NO)(CN)_5].H_2O$ by two molecules of L or one molecule of $L-L$, is facilitated by the *trans*-effect⁸ of the NO group. The resulting compounds (Table 1), are non-hygroscopic, air-stable coloured solids. They are

soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in water. They decompose in dilute acids and alkalis only on heating. All the compounds after decomposition with KOH, followed by acidifying with acetic acid, give a pink colour with Griess reagent⁹. This is probably due to the NO group of the compounds, which after decomposition with alkali changes to NO_2^- , and forms a pink dye with the reagent.

Infrared spectra :

The important infrared spectral bands for the synthesised complexes are discussed below. The appearance of strong bands at 1700–1710 and 2140–2162 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{NO^+} and ν_{CN} respectively, which are in agreement with the results reported elsewhere¹⁰. The positive shift in ν_{NO^+} by ~ 60 cm^{-1} in the complexes compared to the parent compound $K_3[Cr(NO)(CN)_5].H_2O$ (1645 cm^{-1})¹⁰, is probably due to the nature of the co-ligand and non-electrolytic behaviour of the complexes. For convenience of interpretation, the present discussion is divided into two parts.

Complexes of aniline derivatives : A comparison of the ir spectral bands of the free N -alkylanilines and their complexes shows that the ν_{C-N} observed around 1320 cm^{-1} in NMA, NEOT, NEPT, shifted to 1350, 1345 and 1348 cm^{-1} in their respective complexes. In a similar fashion, the ν_{C-N} observed at ~ 1350 cm^{-1} in NNDEMT and NBNEA, shifted to 1380 and 1385 cm^{-1} in their respective complexes. The lowering in ν_{NH} is also observed in the complexes with NMA, NEOT and NEPT. These observations indicate the bonding of nitrogen of aniline derivatives to chromium in the complexes¹¹. The broad bands

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				esr g
		Cr	C	N	N	
1.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (NMA) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	14.35 (14.20)	52.20 52.46	5.57 5.46	19.02 19.12)	1.985
2.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (NEOT) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	12.18 (12.32)	56.91 56.87	6.41 6.63	16.38 16.58)	1.987
3.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (NEPT) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	12.39 (12.32)	56.61 56.87	6.72 6.63	16.69 16.58)	1.984
4.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (NNDEMT) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	10.68 (10.87)	60.12 60.25	7.70 7.53	14.50 14.64)	1.985
5.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (NBNEA) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	9.21 (9.05)	66.62 66.89	6.10 6.27	12.28 12.19)	1.984
6.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (BTMP)(H ₂ O)]	11.51 (11.76)	54.28 54.05	4.20 4.05	15.51 15.76)	1.982
7.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (PRTMP)(H ₂ O)]	13.22 (13.13)	48.29 48.48	4.60 4.54	17.49 17.67)	1.980
8.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (CATMP)(H ₂ O)]	12.30 (12.48)	43.03 43.21	3.75 3.60	16.61 16.80)	1.986
9.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (CBTMP)(H ₂ O)]	10.93 (10.86)	50.25 50.15	3.42 3.55	14.48 14.63)	1.985
10.	[Cr(NO)(CN) ₂ (PHTMP)(H ₂ O)]	11.21 (11.35)	55.29 55.02	4.20 4.36	15.38 15.28)	1.980

*Sl. nos. 1—5 yellowish brown, yield 48–52%, decomp. temp. >300°; sl. nos. 6—10 brownish yellow, yield 44–46%, decomp. temp. >280°.

at 3 560—3 580 and 3 375—3 400 cm⁻¹ for all the complexes are due to ν_{OH} of coordinated water¹².

Complexes of 2-pyrazoline-5-ones: The 2-pyrazoline-5-ones BTMP, PRTMP, CATMP, PHTMP and CBTMP possess two potential donor sites, i.e. the ring carbonyl oxygen and the side-chain carbonyl oxygen. In carbonyl donors, a significant shift of the ν_{CO} to lower wave numbers takes place because of the coordination through carbonyl oxygen. A comparison of the ir spectral bands of the uncoordinated 2-pyrazoline-5-ones and their complexes shows that the ν_{CO} for ring carbonyl observed at 1 600, 1 602, 1 600, 1 605 and 1 600 cm⁻¹ respectively, is shifted to 1 562, 1 558, 1 565, 1 562 and 1 560 cm⁻¹ in the respective complexes. This indicates the bonding of the ring carbonyl oxygen in these ligands to chromium⁴. The side-chain ν_{CO} modes of BTMP (1 642 cm⁻¹), PRTMP (1 648), CATMP (1 652), CBTMP (1 640) and PHTMP (1 675) shifted to 1 602, 1 605, 1 602, 1 605 and 1 615 cm⁻¹, respectively. Therefore, the side-chain carbonyl oxygen also participates in the complexes of these ligands¹³. A broad band at 3 600—3 200 cm⁻¹ for all the complexes, is assigned to coordinated water.

Conductance measurement: The molar conductances measured in 10⁻³ M DMF and MeOH solutions for the complexes of aniline derivatives lie in the range 10.7—13.1 and 7.5—10.5 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ respectively, and in 10⁻³ M EtOH solutions for the complexes of 2-pyrazoline-5-one derivatives in the range 8.5—12.2 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, indicate the non-electrolytic nature of these complexes.

Magnetic studies and esr spectra: The magnetic moment values of the complexes of

aniline derivatives and 2-pyrazolin-5-ones lie in the range 1.70 1.75 and 1.71—1.75 B.M. respectively. The epr data of the complexes are given in Table 1. These values are consistent with a low-spin {CrNO}⁵ electron configuration of chromium(I)¹⁴. Low temperature esr spectra of the complexes, which might give more meaningful data, could not be carried out due to lack of facility.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectral studies were carried out only for the 2-pyrazoline-5-one complexes. They display five bands at 690—710, 405—420, 320—340, 240—250 and 200—210 nm, which may be due to the transitions, 6e→2b₂, 6e→7e, 2b₂→3b₁, 5e→2b₂ and 2b₂→8e respectively, corresponding to hexacoordinated mononitrosyl complexes of C_{4v} symmetry¹⁵.

The analytical data and all the above results suggest the formulation of these complexes as [Cr(NO)(CN)₂(L)₂(H₂O)] (where L=NMA, NEOT, NEPT, NNDEMT or NBNEA) and [Cr(NO)(CN)₂(L-L)(H₂O)] (where L-L=BTMP, PRTMP, CATMP, CBTMP or PHTMP), indicating octahedral structure.

Experimental

Hydroxylammonium chloride and chromic acid (B.D.H.), potassium cyanide (May & Baker), *N*-ethyl-*o*-toluidine, *N*-ethyl-*p*-toluidine, *N,N*-diethyl-*m*-toluidine, *N*-benzyl-*N*-ethylaniline, chloroacetyl chloride, propionyl chloride, phenacyl chloride, *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride and 3-methyl-1-(4'-tolyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (Tokyo Chemical Co.), benzoyl chloride (Ranbaxy) were used as supplied.

The ligands BTMP, PRTMP, CATMP, CBTMP and PHTMP were synthesised by the reported procedure¹⁶ and recrystallised from *n*-heptane.

The parent compound, $K_3[Cr(NO)(CN)_5].H_2O$ was synthesised by following the reported procedure¹⁶.

Synthesis of the complexes. General method : An aqueous acetic acid solution (10 ml, 1 : 1) of the appropriate aniline derivative (0.002 mol)/2-pyrazolin-5-one derivative (0.0 mol) was added with shaking to a filtered aqueous solution of $K_3[Cr(NO)(CN)_5].H_2O$ (0.01 mol, 60 ml). On heating (80°) the mixture for 20–30 min a coloured solid was precipitated. The resulting mixture was freed from the liberated HCN gas by passing a current of CO_2 through the reaction mixture for few hours. The solid was washed with dilute acetic acid and water and dried under reduced pressure over silica gel at room temperature to a constant weight.

Chromium was determined as Cr_2O_3 by the reported method⁸ and C, H and N were determined microanalytically.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the calibrant. Effective magnetic moments were calculated after making diamagnetic corrections¹⁷. Molar conductance was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge.

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Pye-Unicam SP 8-100 spectrophotometer and esr spectra at room temperature on a Varian E-3 spectrometer (9.53 GHz).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to M. P. Council of Science and Technology, Bhopal, for financial assistance.

References

1. J. H. ENEMARK and R. D. FELTHAM, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 13, 389.
2. C. M. LUKCHART and J. N. TROUP, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1977, 22, 81; S. SARKAR, R. C. MAURYA and S. C. CHANRASIA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 285; R. C. MAURYA and R. K. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 340.
3. R. C. MAURYA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 529.
4. R. C. MAURYA and D. D. MISHRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1988, 18, 133; *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, 12, 551.
5. R. C. MAURYA and D. D. MISHRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1989, 13, 533.
6. M. K. CHIMUTOV and N. E. KOCHETKOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1969, 24, 1757; O. NAVRATIL and B. S. JENSEN, *J. Radioanal. Chim.*, 1970, 5, 313.
7. R. H. WILEY and P. WILEY, "Heterocyclic Compounds, Pyrazolones, Pyrazolidines and Derivatives", Interscience, New York, 1964; L. S. GOODMAN and A. GILMAN, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th. ed., Macmillan, London, 1970; "An Encyclopedia of Chemicals, Drugs and Biologicals", 10th. ed., Merck & Co., Rahway, 1983.
8. J. BURGESS, B. A. GOODMAN and J. B. RAYNOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 501.
9. P. GRIESS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1879, 427.
10. W. P. GRIFFITH and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 872.
11. A. D. CROSS, "An Introduction to Practical Infrared Spectroscopy", Butterworth, London, 1960, p. 65.
12. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1978.
13. B. KUNCHERIA and P. INDRASENAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 27, 1005.
14. P. T. MANOHARAM and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 823; L. S. MERIWETHER, S. D. ROBINSON and G. WILKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 1488.
15. B. A. GOODMAN, J. B. RAYNOR and M. C. R. SYMONS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1973.
16. B. S. JENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 1668.
17. R. L. DUTTA and A. SYAMAL, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", S. Chand, New Delhi, 1982.